

The Impact of Education Policy on Teacher Performance among English Teachers: Literature Review

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Abstract: Numerous factors, such as societal, cultural, political, and economic systems, as well as educational institutions, impact education policy and its contextualization. The educational system and structure of a country or region are vital when formulating and carrying out education strategies. Changing the face of education and propelling society forward. Alterations to educational policy have a long history of impacting the evolution of society. More generally, it is believed that the key to national competitiveness and social cohesion lies in investing in education and training. A common strategy for this is to set goals for social progress while simultaneously striving to improve academic achievement. contribute significantly to the development of national unity and competitiveness, often through the pursuit of improved academic outcomes through the formulation of objectives for National competitiveness and social cohesion can be achieved, in theory, through spending money on education and training. Because of the close relationship between an economy's human resource growth and its educational system's development, educational policymaking has a substantial impact on economic growth. The implementation of educational policy in the classroom is directly impacted by the effectiveness of educators. A state's, federal agency's, or city's "education policy implementation" is the dynamic series of actions taken to put into action the stated goals, objectives, and strategies for educational policy.

Introduction

Education policy is influenced by various aspects, including political, economic, social, cultural, and educational systems, which shape a wide range of elements that make up its contextualization. When it comes to creating and implementing education policies, a country or region's educational system and structure are crucial. The relevant departments publish a number of programmatic and guiding documents that are in line with education policy and the course of educational progress within a specific historical period. For activities including teacher cultivation, selection, and training, these papers provide developmental blueprints and action instructions. This study's overarching goal is to examine how junior high schools in Zhongyuan District, Zhengzhou City, China, dealt with teacher professional development as a result of education policy changes that were put into place.

Although there is still a lack of consensus in the literature regarding how exactly education policy affects teachers' professional growth, the vast majority of studies do agree that policy has a substantial impact. Teachers' pedagogical abilities, performance, and other areas of their jobs are improved as a result of this effect. Additionally, with varied participants' histories of initiation, it is challenging to discern between the execution and initiation phases of change

in the context of school-based teacher education development (McBride, 1996). Community organizing, student empowerment, and public accountability are the three pillars upon which the new vision for public education rests (Horsford et al., 2018; Horsford & Horsford, & Horsford, 1996). Over the last 20 years, there has been a significant expansion of our understanding of educational reform (Malone, 2015). One strategy for bringing about this transformation in public schools is the implementation of policies that aim to strengthen student agency, community organizing, and public accountability (Malone, 2015). An international tool for comparing educational achievements across developed nations, the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) was launched in 2000 by the OECD. School reform and systemic changes have been driven by PISA scores and analyses, even though these alone cannot determine the causal relationships between educational inputs and outputs (Schleicher, 2009). Some of the tactics that have contributed to the improvement of education include a core curriculum, more school autonomy, new national evaluation systems, and national standards (Loveless, 2012).

The government has provided more room and funding for educational growth through policymaking as part of China's reform and opening-up. Among these, we must resolve educational disparities and raise the bar for educators. Reforms in China's economic system, especially after the Third Plenary Session of the Eleventh Central Committee of the Communist Party of China (CPC), have boosted economic growth and achieved educational reform victories by increasing funding for public schools. The degree to which a nation's economic development and the amount of resources it determines are the material basis for determining the degree of educational development. Since the 19th National Congress, China has successively issued a number of policy documents involving the construction of the teaching force, for example, in January 2018, the CPC Central Committee and the State Council issued the Opinions on Comprehensively Deepening the Reform of Teacher Construction in the New Era (hereinafter referred to as "Opinions"), which is the first landmark policy document specifically oriented to the construction of the teaching force issued by the Party Central Committee since the founding of New China, and programmatically clarifies the In February 2018, the Ministry of Education and five other departments issued the Action Plan for the Revitalization of Teacher Education (2018-2022) (hereinafter referred to as the Plan), which addresses the imbalance and insufficiency in the development of teacher education and proposes five key tasks and ten major actions in five dimensions, seeking to strengthen teacher education from the source.

According to the "double-reducing" policy, which was issued in 2021 by the General Office of the State Council and the General Office of the Communist Party of China (CPC), "the education department should guide schools to improve their teaching and management procedures, optimize teaching methods, strengthen teaching management, and enhance students' learning in schools" (Shen, 2021). This policy aims to further reduce the burden of homework for students in compulsory education and the burden of out-of-school training. In order to improve the efficiency of students' learning in schools, the policy recommends that "education departments should guide schools to improve teaching management procedures, optimize teaching methods, strengthen teaching management, and enhance the efficiency of students' learning at school".

The growth of rural education hinges on the caliber of its educators, but this growth is limited by both internal dynamics inside rural schools and external variables such as geography, history, and social structures (Zhu Xiang, 2019). Both the teachers and their immediate social and physical environments have a role in determining how far rural educators can go in their careers (Zhu, 2020). One strategy to keep good instructors and encourage their growth is to foster an environment where they feel comfortable sharing ideas and working together (Li Qiong, 2020). The best strategy to keep and promote teachers is to invest in their professional

development. As a faculty member's academic career progresses, they engage in continuous professional growth (Masoumi, 2018). According to the research, there are certain issues with the way teachers are currently being trained. According to the literature, there are difficulties in the development of teachers at the moment due to causes such as a lack of initiative in their own professional growth, unclear development goals, inadequate motivation, and other issues. Some educators experience a crisis of cultural and professional identity, a lack of professional awareness and professionalism, and a lack of space for professional development due to their own disapproval of the teaching culture and the resources available for professional development. Teachers' professionalism has a significant role in their career advancement as well.

Literature Review

An essential area of study in education is the history of education policy, which documents the educational reform initiatives and policies put forth by different nations and regions throughout the years. People have been looking for solutions to educational difficulties practically since the dawn of civilization. The government, in its pursuit of efficiency, embraced a few of these solutions and used them to advance prescriptive performance standards from on high. Early education policy developed out of some of the more rigid behavioral norms that governments imposed and encouraged from on high. Every advanced nation has always had its own unique approach to teaching and learning, even in antiquity. Confucianism, which placed an emphasis on the cultivation of moral character and cultural inheritance through the cultivation of intellectuals, was the dominant ideology in ancient Chinese education policy. As an illustration, "The way to establish a man is to build virtue and merit" highlights the significance of nurturing abilities and establishing appropriate moral guidelines to foster valuable skills and develop exceptional qualities. Play, in its many manifestations, including word play, ritual, and music, was important to the growth of ancient Greek education policy, which prioritized the development of athletics and philosophy. Play had an inherent connection to children in ancient Greece (D'Angour, 2013). The educational policies of that time were primarily based on ideas passed down from the sages and consisted of ad hoc statements encouraging individuals to better themselves and their performance. There were few overarching educational goals or standards, so only a fraction of these were codified into laws by the government. These laws primarily served to maintain political rule and social stability. Education policies have grown in significance alongside modern states as a means of national leadership. Important historical events in the movement to universalize compulsory education occurred in the 19th and early 20th centuries in the United States and Europe. Notable among these acts was the Education Act (1870) in the United Kingdom and the Yalda Act (1881) in France.

Many communist countries after the mid-20th century pushed Marxist education, instituted mandatory schooling, and included education into their state-planned economic structure. The educational policies of the Soviet Union and Great Leap Forward China, to name a few. In an effort to boost national quality and economic development, some developing nations crafted education policies towards the end of the twentieth century. Educational reform approaches tailored to each country's unique circumstances were commonly implemented in these nations.

A variety of trends have emerged in studies of educational policy in recent years. On the one hand, education policy has been moving toward internationalization as a result of globalization's impact on the field. Education is one area where international information sharing has been steadily growing. A prime example of this is the role that transnational collaboration and international organizations like UNESCO play in shaping educational policy with the goal of advancing global education for all. However, many nations have implemented educational reforms to tackle the difficulties of the 21st century, thanks to the

fast advancements in science, technology, and information technology. Modern educational concepts like STEM education, distance learning, and personalized instruction have recently come to the forefront of education policy discussions.

Revolutionizing education and advancing society. Changing educational policies has a long history of influencing societal development. In a broader sense, it is thought that investing in training and education holds the secret to national competitiveness and social cohesiveness. This is typically done by aiming to raise school performance by establishing goals to promote social advancement. Education and training play a crucial role in fostering social cohesiveness and national competitiveness, frequently by aiming to raise school performance by establishing goals for In a broader sense, it is thought that investing in education and training can lead to national competitiveness and social cohesiveness. This belief is often expressed through efforts to improve school performance, such as setting achievement targets for students and requiring schools to create improvement plans to reach those targets (Les Bell, 2006). Economic growth and social stability are also significantly impacted by education policy reform. Using a three-period overlapping generations model, Yang Shuyue and Chen Zhen discovered that public and family education expenditures are substituted for one another. They also found that increasing public investment in education and subsidizing educational commodities can help Chinese families whose quality of life has declined due to the rising number of children. Education and labor market demand. Supply of instructors, quality of instruction, and student achievement are the three most immediate outcomes of education policy. Various aspects of education policy, including hiring practices, working conditions, and salary levels, impact the number of teachers hired and the number of teachers who leave their positions. Consequently, while formulating education policy, it is frequently just as crucial for lawmakers to consider ways to increase teacher recruitment as it is to address the problem of teacher turnover (Sutcher, 2019). Countries throughout the world have been working to improve the quality of their teaching staff by implementing new education policies and other initiatives in response to the many challenges faced by the profession. In the US, numerous initiatives and programs have been created and executed by the federal government to promote teacher preparation, and the Education Act has provided macro-support for this purpose. Based on the realities of rural education, the state government has implemented a variety of teacher training programs. As a result of teacher personal factors and school environment, it is critical to understand these factors in order to promote sustainable and ethical practices in teacher performance. Despite the growing interest in teacher performance, little is known about the relationship between education and teacher performance in China. Although there has been a lot of recent interest in studying teacher performance, very little has been done to examine the connection between education and teacher performance in China. This is despite the fact that teacher performance is a key indicator of educational policy effectiveness and a significant contributor to teacher development. With 52,300 junior high schools and 52,436,900 students enrolled nationwide, China's compulsory education system has come a long way in recent years. In Zhengzhou City, Henan Province, for example, there are 436 junior high schools with 518,100 pupils. After completing junior high, students in China are divided into two tracks based on their grade: senior high and vocational schools. Junior high is the last year of compulsory schooling in China. The Chinese government's educational policies frequently serve as a baton, pointing the way toward better teaching. Consequently, it is critical to study the effects of education policy on teacher performance. Educators, principals, and policymakers can benefit from a better understanding of the factors affecting teachers' performance, both personally and in the context of their schools, in order to design studies that are both practical and ethical.

How well teachers do their jobs is heavily influenced by educational policy. Recognizing the critical role of teachers is essential for education reform to transcend policy rhetoric and

become a part of teachers' daily work (Biase, 2019). Understanding the global impact of policy language and actions is crucial for informing local decision-making about effective education and for improving teachers' performance (Stanley, 2020). There have been a lot of studies looking at how education policy affects teachers' effectiveness in the classroom, but all of the experts agree that good education policy is essential for raising standards. Yet, it is interesting to observe that there doesn't seem to be any research investigating how education policy affects teachers' performance in the contemporary academic environment. At this point, we are wondering why education policy influences teacher effectiveness. Which educational policies are most effective in raising educator effectiveness? There is a large amount of recent writing that has focused on how education policy affects professional development for educators. The creation of educational programs, the establishment of standards for teacher qualifications, and the restructuring of the curriculum's implementation are all ways in which government parenting policies affect teachers' professional development (Rohman, 2019). Another study highlighted that teachers' lack of intrinsic motivation to learn and their professional growth being hindered is primarily due to the absence of education policies that consistently encourage teacher development (Sun Caixia, Qian Xusheng, 2021). Education policies not only dictate how schools are to be structured, but also how they are to achieve their pedagogical aims, what subjects are to be covered, and how they are to be taught (Tsang, 2023).

The way education policy is put into practice in schools also influences how teachers continue to grow professionally. According to Zhuo Tingting (2021), a significant number of public junior high schools in certain regions of China prioritize student development over teacher development. These schools see increasing the school's "advancement rate" as their management goal, which means that professional development of teachers isn't getting the attention it needs. Reform initiatives to enhance the standard of education are the center of global interest. Teachers need additional funding and focus on professional development opportunities. Although there is a wealth of literature on the topic of how education policies impact teacher development, it is worth noting that many of these studies fail to provide clear details about how these policies really affect teacher development. There is a noticeable absence of information regarding how education policy actually affects teacher development in most of the published works. Both the teacher's own characteristics and the conditions in the classroom have a direct impact on the quality of instruction students get. The two most important aspects of the school's integrated environment are the support from administration and the school's culture. Principals' leadership, work environment, and affiliation motivation closely related to the performance of certified teachers; hence teacher's performance can be improved through the leadership of principals and a conducive work environment. Organizations should provide support to the teachers' performance through the leadership of principals and a conducive work environment (Hartinah, 2020). The researchers believe that there is a need to have a need to study the impact of principals' leadership, academic supervision, and professional competence on teachers' performance, which are considered to be determinants of teachers' performance (Dewi Kartini, 2020; Hartinah, 2020; Michael Baptiste, 2019; Parveen, Quang Bao Tran, Kumar, Farooqi (2019) and Kurniadi (2020) cite additional research that finds a favorable correlation between school culture and teacher performance, and they go on to say that teachers' performance improves when principals have more visionary leadership. While these works have examined the effects of professional development on educators, nobody has yet looked at the causes of this phenomenon or how it impacts educators' ability to do their jobs well. Much of the existing research also centers on instructors' intrinsic motivation, which is a key component in determining teachers' success. There was a favorable correlation between teacher effectiveness and five personality traits: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and emotional stability. This was particularly true for assessments of teaching, extraversion, conscientiousness, and

emotional stability. There was a negative correlation between burnout and extraversion and conscientiousness (Klassen, 2019). Among these factors, the impact of teachers' emotional intelligence on their performance was the most noticeable. Studies have shown a positive correlation between teachers' emotional intelligence and their performance, and teachers who score higher on this measure tend to be more dedicated to their teaching and less likely to consider leaving the field (Klassen, 2019; Wahyudi, 2018; Yingying Wu, 2019). Finally, teachers' ability to strike a healthy work-life balance is highly important for their professional development and, as a result, has a significant impact on their students' academic achievement (Rothbard, Beetz, & Harari, 2021). The stress levels of teachers might be negatively affected by an imbalance between their personal lives and their professional duties, which in turn affects their performance in the classroom (Klassen, 2019).

Discussion

An indispensable field of inquiry in education is the history of education policy, which chronicles the educational reform endeavors and policies implemented by many nations and regions over time. Since the beginning of civilization, individuals have been searching for solutions to challenges in education. In order to improve efficiency, the government adopted a number of these solutions and implemented them to establish strict performance criteria from a higher authority. Early education policy emerged as a result of the strict behavioral standards that governments enforced and promoted. Throughout history, every developed country has consistently employed its own distinct methodology for education, even in ancient times. Confucianism, the prevailing ideology in ancient Chinese education policy, prioritized the development of moral character and cultural heritage through the nurturing of intellectuals. "The way to establish a man is to build virtue and merit" emphasizes the importance of cultivating abilities and creating moral principles to promote useful capabilities and develop remarkable attributes. Various forms of play, including as word play, ritual, and music, played a significant role in the advancement of ancient Greek education policy, which emphasized the cultivation of sports and philosophy. According to D'Angour (2013), play was naturally linked to children in ancient Greece. The educational policies of that era were predominantly derived from the wisdom of the sages and comprised of impromptu declarations that motivated individuals to enhance their own growth and achievements. There were a limited number of comprehensive educational objectives or standards, resulting in only a small portion of them being officially established as laws by the government. These laws primarily aimed to uphold political governance and ensure societal equilibrium. Education policies have been increasingly important in conjunction with the development of modern states as a method of guiding the nation. Significant historical milestones in the effort to establish mandatory education for all took place during the 19th and early 20th century in the United States and Europe. Significant among these legislations was the Education Act (1870) in the United Kingdom and the Yalda Act (1881) in France.

Several communist nations in the post-1950s era actively promoted Marxist education, implemented compulsory schooling, and integrated education into their centrally planned economic framework. Examples of educational policies include those implemented in the Soviet Union and during the Great Leap Forward in China. During the late twentieth century, certain emerging countries formulated education strategies with the aim of enhancing national quality and promoting economic growth. These nations typically implemented educational reform measures that were customized to suit the specific circumstances of each country. In recent years, there has been a proliferation of trends in the field of educational policy research. Education policy has been increasingly embracing internationalization due to the influence of globalization. The exchange of information in the field of education has been consistently expanding on a worldwide scale. An exemplary instance of this phenomenon is the essential role that transnational cooperation and international organizations, such as

UNESCO, assume in influencing educational policy with the aim of promoting universal education worldwide. Nevertheless, numerous countries have enacted educational changes to address the challenges of the 21st century, owing to the rapid progress in science, technology, and information technology. Contemporary educational ideas such as STEM education, distance learning, and individualized instruction have recently been prominent topics in conversations about education policy.

Transforming education and propelling society forward. The alteration of educational policy has a lengthy record of exerting an impact on the progress of society. From a broader perspective, it is believed that allocating resources towards training and education is the key to achieving national competitiveness and social cohesiveness. Typically, this is achieved by setting objectives to enhance academic achievement and facilitate upward social mobility. They have a significant impact on promoting social unity and national competitiveness, often by striving to improve academic achievement through the establishment of specific objectives for schools. From a broader perspective, it is believed that allocating resources towards education and training can enhance a nation's competitiveness and foster social cohesion. This notion is frequently demonstrated by initiatives aimed at enhancing academic performance, such as establishing specific goals for students and mandating schools to develop improvement strategies to accomplish those goals (Les Bell, 2006). Education policy reform has a substantial impact on both economic growth and social stability. Yang Shuyue and Chen Zhen found that public and family education expenditures are interchangeable in a three-period overlapping generations model. Additionally, it was shown that augmenting state expenditure on education and providing subsidies for educational goods can assist Chinese households whose standard of living has deteriorated as a result of the growing number of children.

The correlation between education and job market demand. The three primary consequences of education policy are the provision of instructors, the caliber of instruction, and the academic performance of students. Multiple facets of education policy, such as recruitment procedures, job environment, and remuneration levels, influence the recruitment and attrition rates of teachers. Hence, when developing education policies, it is equally important for lawmakers to prioritize strategies for enhancing teacher recruitment, alongside addressing the issue of teacher turnover (Sutcher, 2019). Nations worldwide have been endeavoring to enhance the caliber of their teaching personnel by enacting novel educational policies and undertaking various efforts in response to the numerous issues encountered by the profession. In the United States, the federal government has implemented several efforts and programs to enhance teacher preparation. The Education Act has played a significant role in providing broad support for this objective. The state government has created several teacher training programs in response to the challenges faced in rural education.

In order to develop sustainable and ethical practices in teacher performance, it is crucial to have a comprehensive understanding of the personal elements of teachers and the school environment. Although there is a rising interest in teacher performance, there is less knowledge regarding the correlation between schooling and teacher performance in China. Despite the current surge in interest regarding the study of teacher performance, there has been a notable lack of research investigating the correlation between education and teacher performance in China. However, it is important to note that the performance of teachers plays a crucial role in determining the success of educational policies and greatly influences the growth and improvement of teachers. China's compulsory education system has made significant progress in recent years, with a total of 52,300 junior high schools and an enrollment of 52,436,900 pupils nationwide. For instance, in Zhengzhou City, located in Henan Province, there are a total of 436 junior high schools, accommodating a student population of 518,100. Upon finishing junior high, children in China are segregated into two

distinct educational paths, namely senior high schools and vocational schools, based on their academic performance. Junior high represents the final year of mandatory education in China.

The educational policies of the Chinese government often function as a guide, indicating the path towards improved teaching. Therefore, it is essential to examine the impact of education policy on teacher performance. To create studies that are practical and ethical, educators, principals, and policymakers should have a comprehensive grasp of the elements that influence teachers' performance, both on a personal level and within the school environment. Educational policy exerts a significant influence on the performance of teachers in their professional roles. It is crucial to acknowledge the vital importance of teachers in order for education reform to go beyond mere policy talk and actually be integrated into teachers' everyday tasks (Biase, 2019). Gaining a comprehensive understanding of how policy language and actions affect the world as a whole is essential for guiding local decision-making on effective education and enhancing teachers' effectiveness (Stanley, 2020). Numerous research have examined the impact of education policy on teachers' efficacy in the classroom. Consensus among experts affirms that high-quality education policy is crucial for improving standards. However, it is noteworthy that there is a lack of research examining the impact of education policy on teachers' performance in the current academic setting. Currently, we are pondering the reasons behind the impact of education policy on teacher effectiveness. Which educational policies are most efficacious in enhancing educator efficacy?

Considerable attention has been given to the relationship between education policy and the enhancement of professional development for educators in recent literature. Government parenting policies impact teachers' professional development through the execution of educational programs, the formulation of criteria for teacher qualifications, and the reorganization of curriculum implementation (Rohman, 2019). A further study emphasized that teachers' insufficient internal drive to acquire knowledge and their limited opportunities for professional advancement are mainly caused by the absence of education policies that consistently promote teacher development (Sun Caixia, Qian Xusheng, 2021). Education policies govern the organization and operation of schools, as well as the methods and subjects used to attain educational goals (Tsang, 2023).

The implementation of education policy in schools has a significant impact on the ongoing professional development of teachers. Zhuo Tingting (2021) states that in specific locations of China, a considerable proportion of public junior high schools prioritize the growth and progress of students over the growth and progress of teachers. These schools prioritize improving the school's "advancement rate" as their management objective, resulting in insufficient attention given to the professional development of teachers. Global attention is focused on reform measures aimed at improving the quality of education. Teachers require supplementary support and a concentrated emphasis on professional development opportunities. While there is an abundance of literature regarding the influence of education policies on teacher development, it is important to acknowledge that many of these studies lack explicit information on the actual impact of these policies on teacher development. Most published papers lack information on how education policy directly impacts teacher development. Both the teacher's personal attributes and the classroom environment directly influence the quality of instruction received by students. The primary elements that contribute significantly to the school's integrated environment are the backing from the administration and the prevailing culture inside the institution. The performance of certified instructors is closely linked to the leadership of principals, the work environment, and their incentive to be affiliated with the school. Therefore, improving the performance of teachers may be achieved by effective leadership from principals and creating a favorable work environment.

Organizations must to offer assistance to teachers' performance by means of effective leadership from principals and a favorable work environment (Hartinah, 2020).The

researchers argue that it is necessary to examine the influence of principals' leadership, academic supervision, and professional competence on teachers' performance, as these factors are considered to be key determinants of teachers' effectiveness (Dewi Kartini, 2020; Hartinah, 2020; Michael Baptiste, 2019; Parveen, Quang Bao Tran, Kumar, Farooqi, 2019; Kurniadi, 2020). Additionally, Parveen et al. (2019) and Kurniadi (2020) cite other studies that demonstrate a positive correlation between school culture and teacher performance, suggesting that teachers' performance improves when principals exhibit more visionary leadership. Although previous studies have explored the impact of professional development on educators, no research has yet investigated the underlying causes of this phenomena or its influence on educators' job performance. A significant portion of the current research also focuses on the inherent drive of instructors, which plays a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of teachers. A positive link was observed between teacher effectiveness and five specific personality traits: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and emotional stability. This was especially accurate for evaluations of teaching, extraversion, conscientiousness, and emotional stability. A study conducted by Klassen in 2019 found a clear negative relationship between burnout and both extraversion and conscientiousness. Out of all these factors, the influence of teachers' emotional intelligence on their performance was the most prominent. Research has demonstrated a direct link between teachers' emotional intelligence and their job performance. Teachers who exhibit greater levels of emotional intelligence are more committed to their teaching profession and less like to contemplate quitting (Klassen, 2019; Wahyudi, 2018; Yingying Wu, 2019). Teachers' capacity to achieve a harmonious equilibrium between work and personal life is crucial for their professional growth and has a substantial influence on their students' academic performance (Rothbard, Beetz, & Harari, 2021). An asymmetry between teachers' personal lives and professional responsibilities may have an adverse impact on their stress levels, therefore influencing their classroom performance (Klassen, 2019).

Conclusion

There is a strong correlation between the growth of a nation's human resources and the development of its educational system, which means that educational policymaking significantly affects national development. The effectiveness of educators has a direct bearing on how educational policies are put into action in the classroom. The term "education policy implementation" refers to the ever-changing operational process by which the state, federal, and municipal governments' stated aims, objectives, and plans for educational policy are translated into concrete steps to address educational policy issues. For instance, the Chinese government's 2021 opinions on Further Reducing the Burden of Homework for Students in Compulsory Education and the Burden of Out-of-School Training had a significant impact on the content, duration, and goals of Chinese students' education, leading to changes in teachers' pedagogical responsibilities as a result. This shift in policy regarding education has an effect on teachers' performance patterns. However, there are policies that have an impact on teachers' performance. For example, China's education policy, which is relatively static, includes the Code of Conduct for Teachers and the Code of Conduct for Primary and Secondary School Teachers. These documents set standards for how teachers should conduct themselves in the classroom and how they should interact with students. Research on the elements influencing teacher effectiveness in the classroom, including school culture and individual teacher characteristics.

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